

A STUDY TO ASSESS THE ATTITUDE TOWARDS CORPORAL PUNISHMENT AND PRACTICE OF POSITIVE DISCIPLINE AMONG PARENTS IN SELECTED URBAN AREA BENGALURU, WITH A VIEW TO DEVELOP AN INFORMATION BOOKLET

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ABSTRACT

Background & Objectives: Corporal punishment of children breaches their fundamental human rights to respect for human dignity and physical integrity. Assess the attitude towards corporal punishment & expressed practice of positive discipline among parents. There is a need for parents to have knowledge regarding corporal punishment and how to discipline the children. **Methods:** A Non-Experimental descriptive study design was used. Data was collected from 100 parents of children between the age group of 3-12years in Roopena Agrahara, Bengaluru. Non probability purposive sampling technique was used. Self-administered attitude scale and practice checklist was used to collect the needed data. **Results:** The mean score was 38.05 with SD was 12.036 and the mean percentage was 63.41% towards corporal punishment & the

mean score of practice of positive discipline was 14.92 and SD was 5.3154 with a mean percentage of 59.68 %. **Interpretation and Conclusion:** The attitude related to corporal punishment among 100 samples of parents 38% had strongly favorable attitude, 30% had favorable attitude and 32% had unfavorable attitude. The practice related positive discipline among 100 samples of parents 54% had satisfactory practice and 46% had unsatisfactory practice. There is a need for primary prevention through interventional program to control the negative effects of harsh disciplinary methods. Hence it is concluded that there is a need to develop/provide information booklet to parents is essential in this regard.

KEYWORDS: Corporal punishment, attitude, practice, positive discipline, information booklet.

INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

Children are the little angels in the world and they need assistance from parents. Parents have to understand the challenging needs of children in their physical, emotional, mental and social aspects.^[1] Discipline is an attitude, character, responsibility or commitment. The discipline is basically internal, while the attempt to impose it would be an external process. Discipline is the practice of training people to obey rules or a code of behavior, using punishment to correct disobedience. Positive discipline is a way of teaching and guiding children by letting them know what behavior is acceptable in a way that is firm, yet kind. A positive discipline shape a child's behavior and helps them to learn any control, when it provides encouragement not painful meaningless consequences.

The committee on the rights of child in the general Comment No.7 defines corporal or physical punishment such as any punishment in which physical force is used and intended to cause some degree of pain or discomfort however light most involves hitting, smacking, slapping, and spanking, children with the hand or with an implement. In view of the committee, corporal punishment is invariably degrading.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To assess the attitude towards corporal punishment among parents.
- To assess the practice of positive discipline among parents.
- To find the association between attitude towards corporal punishment and selected demographic variables.
- To find the association between practice of positive discipline and selected demographic variables.

HYPOTHESIS

- **H₁**:- There will be significant association between attitude towards corporal punishment and selected demographic variables.
- **H₂**:- There will be significant association between practice of positive discipline and selected demographic variables.

Variables Under Study

Research Variables: Attitude towards corporal punishment and Practice of positive discipline.

Demographic Variables: Age, Sex, Education, Family Income, Religion, Type of family, Type of disciplinary methods used.

Conceptual frame work

The conceptual framework of the present study was based on Von Bertalanffy's (1968) general system Theory. This study adopted Non-experimental descriptive research design

METHODOLOGY

In order to achieve the objectives of the study exploratory survey approach was found to be appropriate and selected for the study. Depending upon the purpose of the study, research approach and variables to be studied, descriptive design was adopted for the present study, as it was a virtue of a situation that naturally happens.

Inclusion Criteria

- Parents who are having children ages between 3-12 years.
- Parents who are available at the time of data collection.
- Parents who are able to read and write English and kannada.

Exclusion Criteria

- Parents who are not available during data collection.
- Parents who are not willing to participate in this study.

Tool used for the study

SECTION –A: Demographic data

This section consists of 7 items seeking personal information such as Age, Relationship with the child, Educational, Family Income, Religion, Type of family, Type of disciplinary methods used.

SECTION-B: Attitude scale

3 point Likert scale prepared with attitude statements regarding corporal punishment. It consists of 30 statements and 3 columns such as strongly agree, Agree, Disagree. Score for each statement are as follows:

FOR STATEMENTS	POSITIVE	NEGATIVE
STRONGLY FAVOURABLE	2	0
FAVOURABLE	1	0
UNFAVOURABLE	0	0

The resulting score were ranged as follows

UNFAVOURABLE: < 30

FAVOURABLE: 30-45

MOST FAVOURABLE: 45-60

SECTION-B: Check list to assess the practice of positive discipline among parents of children between the age group of 3-12years

It consists of 25 statements and 2 columns such as YES and NO. Scores for each statement are as follows

YES: 1

NO: 0

The resulting score were ranged as follows:

SATISFACTORY: >12

UNSATISFACTORY: <12

Procedure for data collection

Before collecting the data, permission was obtained from the concerned authority. Keeping in mind that the ethical aspect of research, the data was collected after obtaining the informed consent from the sample. The samples were assured anonymity and confidentiality of information provided by them. The study was carried out by the researcher for 3weeks who fulfilled the inclusion criteria were selected and assessment on corporal punishment and practice of positive discipline was done. The investigator collected data and distributed an information booklet on positive discipline.

RESULTS: SECTION -I

Table – 1: Findings related to Types of disciplinary methods used by parents

n=100

Types of disciplinary methods used	Frequency	Percentage %
Beating	45	45
Rewarding	20	20
Over protective	15	15

Kind and firm	20	20
Total	100	100

SECTION II

Attitude of parents regarding corporal punishment

Fig1: The cylindrical diagram showing classification of parents based on their attitude towards corporal punishment.

This diagram depicts that 38 (38%) had most favorable attitude, 30(30%) had favorable attitude and 32 (32%) had un favorable attitude.

DISCIPLINE

SECTION III

Classification of respondents based on the Practice of Positive

Fig. 2: The pie diagram showing practice of parents regarding Positive Discipline.

This pie diagram depicts that 54 (54%) had satisfactory practice, 46 (46%) had unsatisfactory practice.

Table 2 Shows that the mean score of attitude towards corporal punishment.

n = 100

S.No	No. of questions	Max. score	Range	Mean	Median	SD	Mean percentage
1	30	60	12-59	38.05	39.5	12.036	63.41

Table 3 Shows that the mean score of practice of positive discipline

n = 100

S. No	No. of questions	Max. score	Range	Mean	Median	SD	Mean percentage
1	25	25	8-24	14.92	15	5.3154	59.68

SECTION IV

Findings related to association of attitude with selected demographic variables.

Table 4: Association of attitude scores with selected demographic variables.

n=100

Sl No	Demographic Variables	No%		ATTITUDE SCORE						Chi Square X ²	DF	P Value	Inference		
				Strongly favourable		Favourable		Un favourable							
				No	%	No	%	No	%						
1	Age in years											14.4139	6	0.025339	S
a	23-27	18	18	8	8	6	6	4	4						
b	27-31	25	25	12	12	8	8	5	5						
c	31-35	32	32	15	15	9	9	8	8						
d	Above 35	25	25	3	3	7	7	15	15						
2	Relationship to the child											0.6196	2	0.733592	NS
a	Father	28	28	10	10	10	10	8	8						
b	Mother	72	72	28	28	20	20	24	24						
3	Educational status											3.3038	6	0.769869	NS
a	Higher Secondary	20	20	8	8	4	4	8	8						
b	Diploma	25	25	9	9	9	9	7	7						
c	Degree	35	35	12	12	10	10	3	3						
d	Master degree	20	20	9	9	7	7	4	4						
4	Religion											5.1086	4	0.276337	NS
a	Hindu	72	72	25	25	20	25	27	27						
b	Muslim	18	18	9	9	5	5	4	4						
c	Christian	10	10	4	4	5	5	1	1						
5	Type of family											5.535	4	0.23667	NS
a	Nuclear	42	42	13	13	14	14	15	15						

b	Joint	50	50	19	19	15	15	16	16				
	Extended	8	8	6	6	1	1	1	1				
6	Monthly Income												
a	10001 – 15000	22	22	10	10	4	4	8	8	9.4056	6	0.152018	NS
b	15001 – 20000	26	26	9	9	7	7	9	9				
c	20001 – 25000	27	27	8	8	7	7	12	12				
d	Above 25000	25	25	11	11	12	12	3	3				
7	Type of disciplinary method used												
a	Beating	45	45	13	13	17	17	15	15	13.3471	6	0.037843	S
b	Rewarding	20	20	9	9	2	2	9	9				
c	Over protective	15	15	10	10	2	2	3	3				
d	Kind & firm	20	20	6	6	9	9	5	5				

SECTION-V

Findings related to association of practice with selected demographic variables.

Table 5: Association of practice with selected demographic variables.

n=100

Sl No	Demographic Variables	No	%	Practice score				Chi Square χ^2	DF	P Value	Inference
				Satisfactory factor (54)		Unsatisfactory factor (46)					
				No	%	No	%				
1	Age in years										
a	23-27	18	18	9	9	9	9	0.5284	3	0.912613	NS
b	28-31	25	25	15	15	10	10				
c	32-35	32	32	17	17	15	15				
d	Above 35	25	25	13	13	12	12				
2	Relationship to the child										
a	Father	28	28	18	18	10	10	1.6563	1	0.198102	NS
b	Mother	72	72	36	36	36	36				
3	Educational status										
a	Higher Secondary	20	20	12	12	8	8	7.3614	3	0.061229	NS
b	Diploma	25	25	8	8	17	17				
c	Degree	35	35	20	20	15	15				
d	Master Degree	20	20	14	14	6	6				

Findings

The findings of the study had been discussed with reference to the objectives and hypotheses stated in introduction and in relation with the findings of other studies. The aim of the study

was to assess the attitude towards corporal punishment and practice of positive discipline among parents in selected urban area Bengaluru with a view to develop an information booklet.

DISCUSSION

Findings related to the attitude of parents related to corporal punishment. Among 100 samples of parents 38% had most favorable attitude, 30 % had favorable attitude and 32 % had unfavorable attitude.

The findings of the present study were supported by a study conducted India.

The goal of the study was to determine parental attitudes concerning the use of physical punishment in homes behavior. 34% of parents believed corporal punishment would improve behavior, and 20% of parents felt that physical punishment would improve their child's academic performance.

Findings related to the practice of parents related positive discipline

Among 100 samples of parents 54% had satisfactory practice and 46% had unsatisfactory practice. The findings of the present study were supported by a quasi-experimental design was conducted assess the effectiveness of parenting education program on parental ability to use positive behavior control strategies among 150 parents in Nigeria south Africa. The study showed that the significant treatment effect on parenting behavior $F(2, 248) = 23.39, p < .05$, with the intervention parents demonstrating greater ability to use positive behavior control strategies than did the comparison parents. The study concluded that the parenting education program could be effective in helping parents to improve their parenting skills and support them in creating a safe and supportive home environment that prevent children's exposure to physical abuse.

Findings related to association of attitude with selected demographic variables

The hypothesis H_1 stating there will be significant association between attitude on corporal punishment with selected demographic variables was accepted.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the present study, the recommendations offered for the future research is:

- Similar study can be conducted on large sample.

- Similar study can be conducted on school teachers and other care givers of children.
- Further research can be conducted by using other methods of education programs aided with videos, leaflets, educational programmes etc.
- Comparative study can be conducted.
- Evaluative study can be done.

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